

Deliverable D5.1 (D16): Project *Website* and Social Media *presence*

Submission date: March 24th 2020
Version: 1.0
Document type: Report
Dissemination level: Public
Grant Agreement number: 862882
Project acronym: IN-FET

Revision history:

Version	Date	Authors	Organisation	Description
1.0	20 March 2020	Michele Giugliano	SISSA	Initial draft
1.5	23 March 2020	Luca Selmi Renaud Jolivet	IUNET UNIGE	Amendments after feedback from partners
2.0	27 March 2020	Michele Giugliano	SISSA	Final version

Tasks related to this deliverable:

Task No.	Task Description	Partners involved
T5.1	Management	SISSA, ALL
T5.3	Dissemination and networking	SISSA, ALL

1. Project *website* and social-media *presence*

The participants to the IN-FET project consortium are well aware that the generous funding from the European Commission is a direct consequence of taxpayers' money. With this in mind, the dissemination and outreach activities, targeting both the scientific community and the general public, are key priorities of the consortium.

Deliverable 16, due by month 3 (i.e. 31st March 2020), consists in the creation and initial update of i) a presence on the Internet with a dedicated website as well as of ii) visibility in social media. As originally intended, these channels are aimed at the general public, as well as at the scientific community, and they will act as a dissemination channel for the IN-FET consortium. During the first weeks of 2020 (i.e. month 1-2) we thus launched and started using

- a website (<https://www.in-fet.eu>)
- a dedicated Twitter account (http://twitter.com/fet_in)
- a dedicated Facebook page (<https://www.facebook.com/infetproject>)
- a dedicated YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4299VceGDOSVqmFTgHTIEw>)

Most of these communication channels have been already populated with preliminary information, as well as *ad hoc* press releases and launch announcements. They will be further developed and maintained updated through time, reflecting the progress of the project's activities. Their main purposes are the presentation of the consortium, an introduction of its joint science and innovation coordinated activities in the context of the IN-FET project, as well as the rapid dissemination of scientific and outreach products.

The target audience of all these communication channels is represented by colleague scientists and researchers in Europe and world-wide working in the same or different domains of research, and the general public. The website has been built using Drupal, a widely used open-source content-management system (CMS) for online digital experiences that reach the target audiences across in

the most effective ways for both desktop and mobile device users. Below some screenshots of the website content currently implemented.

The Twitter account has been first created in 2019, connected to other strategic accounts and (FET) projects, and already populated with several “tweets”. Below we report a screen shot of its main

profile page, including the statistics related to a representative announcement (i.e. the joint press-release, of the kick-off in Feb 2020). This tweet resulted in an engagement of more than 2'000 people.

Finally, a Facebook page has been created as well, but for reasons related to the social platform, it remains less visible and discoverable than Twitter, unless explicit payments for active ads are made to Facebook. We have thus decided that Twitter and YouTube will become our main social media presence, together of course with the project website. The YouTube platform will soon host the *ad*

hoc video introduction of our project consortium, which will be subcontracted to an external company in Switzerland.

Additionally, members of the consortium active on social media have been already posting news about the project on other social media platforms such as LinkedIn. These posts have had a wide reach with hundreds of impressions each. Some screenshots are appended below.

Renaud Jolivet

Group Leader in Neurophysics

1mo • 🌐

Kickoff meeting of the IN-FET project (<http://in-fet.eu>) in SISSA, Trieste! Follow us here and on Twitter (@fet_eu) to learn about the future of brain-machine interfaces and neuromodulation!

...see more

👍 25 · 2 Comments

👍 Like 💬 Comment ➦ Share

📈 829 views of your post in the feed

Renaud Jolivet
Group Leader in Neurophysics
1mo • 🌐

Read SISSA's press release about our new H2020 FET-Open project!

[#horizon2020](#) [#fetopen](#) [#bci](#) [#epilepsy](#)

SISSA
Scuola
Internazionale
Superiore di
Studi Avanzati

IU.NET

**UNIVERSITÉ
DE GENÈVE**

**multichannel
systems**

PRESS RELEASE

EU Funds €3M Project to Develop Nanodevices against Epilepsy and Parkinson's

Novel nanotechnologies could be used as brain implants, modulating the activity of nerve cells electrochemically and treating neurological diseases like **epilepsy and Parkinson's**. This is the goal of a three-year, **€3 million project financed by the European Commission** and led by SISSA with collaborative partners including: IBM Research, the Universities of Geneva and Sheffield, Multi Channel Systems, and the Italian Inter-University Consortium for Nanoelectronics with University of Modena and Reggio Emilia and University of Udine

4 February 2020

*Epilepsy is one of the most common neurological diseases, affecting 50 million people worldwide. Pharmacological treatment is a widespread approach to fight the disease but for many patients medication is no help. Epilepsy drugs prove ineffective with 7% to 20% of children ailed by the condition. Drug resistance amongst adults ranges between 30% and 40%. Alternative experimental therapies also have serious drawbacks. IN-FET project ("Ion Neuromodulation for Epilepsy Treatment") aims to develop new nanodevices that could be used as brain implants to modulate the electrical

🔗 ❤️ 8 • 1 Comment

👍 Like 💬 Comment ➦ Share

📈 835 views of your post in the feed

2. Conclusions and outlook

The implemented website and social media presence obviously represent only the starting point for an effective dissemination and networking campaign that will be fully deployed as soon as the project will start achieving its key milestones and results. We also plan to make the platforms an effective engagement tool for the RRI initiatives foreseen by the project programme.